

ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEMS EXISTING IN THE OPERATIONS OF ACADEMIC COMMITTEES IN LOCAL MEDICAL COLLEGES AND UNIVERSITIES: A CASE STUDY

Fu Jiayi^{1*}, Esayas Teshome Taddese²

^{1,2}Faculty of Education and Humanities, UNITAR International University, Tierra Crest, Jalan SS6/3, Kelana Jaya, 47301 Petaling Jaya, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Malaysia

*Corresponding authors: mc230723079@student.unitar.my

Received Date: 20/03/2024

Accepted Date: 20/05/2024

Published Date: 30/06/2024

ABSTRACT

Despite the national policy guidance and university documents, academic committees of local medical colleges and universities in China still need improvement. Academic committees cannot give full play to their role, which seriously affects the level of academic governance and the overall development of universities. This qualitative case study examines the problems in the operation of the Academic Committee in a local medical university from the perspective of team performance management and discusses the underlying reasons. The study used a purposive sampling method to select five members of the Academic Committee and five administrative staff from a local medical university in Shandong Province, China, as participants. The researcher collected data through interviews. After analyzing the data combined with the team performance management model, the problems were concentrated in the following aspects: the positioning of the Academic Committee was unclear; the composition was unreasonable; the operation mechanism was not sound; there were differences in the ability of members to perform their duties; ignoring stakeholders; team and individual lacked reflection and improvement. Based on the perspective of the Secretariat of the Academic Committee, the researcher put forward several suggestions. These findings and recommendations would help the Academic Committee in the case to improve and enhance operational efficiency in the next transition.

Keywords: academic committees, local medical university

INTRODUCTION

Article 42 of the Higher Education Law of the People's Republic of China (revised in 2018) stipulates that higher education institutions shall establish academic committees and perform relevant duties. To promote institutions of higher education to standardize and strengthen the construction of academic committees, improve the internal governance structure, and ensure that academic committees play an influential role in academic affairs such as teaching and scientific research,

the Ministry of Education promulgated the Regulations on Academic Committees of Institutions of Higher Education in 2014, which further stipulated the composition, duties, and operation of academic committees of colleges and universities. Higher education institutions should set up academic committees according to the law and improve the academic management system and organizational structure with academic committees as the core. Academic committees, as the highest academic institution in universities, coordinate the decision-making, deliberation, evaluation, and consultation of academic affairs (Article 2).

Despite the guidance, in practice, "the role of academic committees is not fully played" and "the administrative power of colleges and universities is strong" have been criticized as a realistic situation (Wang & Ruan, 2022). In many universities, academic committees have only symbolic significance. They face the embarrassment of being unused or marginalized, their operating space is squeezed, and the academic governance function is rarely demonstrated substantively (Wang & Wang, 2022).

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Most studies on academic organizations have focused on ministry-affiliated universities, with few dealings with local universities organized by local provinces and cities. The governance system of local universities is different from that of ministry-affiliated universities. There is still much room for improvement in implementing the power and function of academic committees in local colleges and universities due to the limitation of governance ability and academic level. If the development route of ministry-affiliated universities is copied, it may lead to the phenomenon of children wearing adults' shoes. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze and study the academic committees of local universities with slow development.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Despite the policy guidance issued by the state and relevant departments and the continuous revision of the constitution and rules of procedure of academic committees by universities, the function of academic committees is still unsatisfactory. This paper aims to study the problems existing in the operation of the Academic Committee and analyze the deep reasons from the perspective of how to run the Academic Committee efficiently. At the same time, this research plan explores relevant optimization strategies based on the view of the Secretariat of the Academic Committee to help the Academic Committee give full play to its academic governance function and further enhance its role.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study addresses the following research questions:

1. What are the problems in the operation of the Academic Committee?
2. Analyze the deep causes of the above problems from the perspective of efficient operation of the Academic Committee.

3. What strategies can the Secretariat respond to and improve?

LITERATURE REVIEW

THE PROBLEMS IN THE OPERATION OF THE ACADEMIC COMMITTEE

Liao (2019), Yu (2020) and Li et al. (2018) all believed that the authority of academic committees as the highest academic institution had not been effectively exercised and had not played a substantive role in the governance of the university.

From the perspective of academic and administrative power, Liao (2019) believes there was a lack of interaction between the academic committee, the Party committee and the president's office. Zhang et al. (2020) and Li et al. (2018) found that in the process of academic governance, administrative power often occupies an active position.

Yu and Liu (2023) analyzed the problems of university academic governance from four aspects: committee organization structure, rule constraint, academic committee operation mechanism and supervision mechanism. They believed that the committee members determine the effectiveness of academic governance. The membership structure is the essential "access" provision for participating in academic governance, and it is an internal factor affecting the realization of academic decision-making, deliberation, evaluation and consultation rights and responsibilities. On the other hand, they found that the restriction system of responsibilities and rights of academic governance was not perfect. If there is no institutional guarantee, the power and responsibility of academic governance can only be vacuous.

Through analysis, Tian (2022) believes that the main factors affecting the function of the academic committee of first-class universities were rules and regulations, rights, culture and committee personality. Through investigation, Zhang et al. (2020) found that the reasons for the marginalization of the academic committee were insufficient staffing, weak willingness of members to perform their duties, administrative power squeezing academic power and low university attention.

Li and Su (2020) thought that the imperfect constitution of the academic committee was an important reason that the academic committee could not play its full role. Through the analysis of the charter texts of 22 universities, they found many problems in the charter of the academic committee, such as unclear definition of the responsibilities and powers of the academic committee, unreasonable selection conditions of members, and imperfect organizational structure design.

In addition, the following problems are also frequently mentioned. The relationship between academic governance organizations and functional departments in colleges and universities, with academic committees as the core, needs adjustment Liao (2019). Academic governance organizations are insufficiently diverse in their membership. In practice, the procedures of academic governance are too simple. The decision-making mechanism of academic affairs needs to be standardized. The self-discipline of the academic community needs to be improved (Huang & Lin, 2022). According to Li et al. (2018), in a study of 75 ministry-affiliated universities, the respondents believed that academic committees had weak power, played an insufficient role in academic affairs, and lacked appropriate organizational structures and dedicated staff. Liu and

Wang (2021) cited a survey of more than 200 public universities nationwide. The researchers investigated the role of academic committees in significant university decisions. The survey results showed that the respondents generally believed that academic committees mainly play an advisory role in the decision-making process of important academic affairs such as personnel training, scientific research, discipline construction, personnel work planning and personnel policies, significant cooperation and exchanges at home and abroad, the application of teaching and research projects and the allocation and use of funds, and the staff post responsibility system. It only played a deliberative role in the establishment of academic disciplines. Wei (2016) pointed out that a common phenomenon is that while emphasizing the role of professors, young and middle-aged teachers and students are ignored, which does not reflect the community composed of teachers and students. According to a study by Guo and Sun (2020), the relationship between the academic committee and other external academic institutions was not properly organized, resulting in unclear responsibilities.

STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE THE OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF ACADEMIC COMMITTEES

Some scholars put forward opinions and suggestions from the university and faculty grading management perspective:

Based on the positioning of the role of academic committees in universities and from the perspective of promoting the effective management of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary affairs, Guo and Sun (2020) believed that the three-level academic committee model of university, department, and faculty is relatively scientific in terms of vertical hierarchy.

Wang (2022) proposed five necessary steps to promote modernizing university internal governance. The first step is to reduce the focus of management to the hospital level. The second step is to strengthen the governance function of academic committees of faculties to be consistent with the strengthening of universities' governance responsibility and adapt to improving the dean's management ability.

Many scholars prefer the concept of co-governance rather than the separation of administrative power and academic power:

Liu and Wang (2021) believed that to truly participate in the decision-making process and play a more critical role in the scope of their fields, the important stakeholders of universities also need to hope for the further deepening of the reform and carry out innovation and protection from the institutional level.

Zhang and Yue (2019) did not believe that the president can "de-administration" if the president does not participate in academic committees, or if the president participates in academic committees, the administrative power will erode the academic power. The president's participation may be conducive to the regular operation of academic power. The practice of diversified governance in universities reflects the complexity of university governance. Also, it shows that to improve the effectiveness of university governance, it is necessary to comprehensively consider and deal with several pairs of relations, such as administrative power and academic power, formal system and informal system, legitimacy and efficiency mechanism.

Based on the marginalization of academic committees in universities, Wang and Wang (2022) proposed a dual-track governance framework of an "administrative incentive track" and an

"academic autonomy track." Its theoretical core lies in forming a "dual-track governance" structure and mechanism that can not only inherit the logic of academic autonomy but also release the function of administrative incentive through the "dual-track system" organizational design and system construction. Therefore, Chinese universities' organisational stability and decision-making effectiveness must be improved to achieve the relative separation and coordination of university administration and academic and professional decision-making.

Tian (2022) pointed out that the "symbiotic" academic committee is the most effective construction model. The "symbiotic" academic committee refers to the academic committee whose members are mainly professors without administrative positions, and the results of the academic committee's decisions can be used as the final decision-making basis.

METHODOLOGY

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study was based on Peter (2011) Hawkins's 5Cs model. He developed a four-box model that connected internal, external, task, and process. Then, five disciplines: commissioning, clarifying, co-creating, connecting, and core learning. He believed high-performing leadership teams must do well in all five disciplines of the 5Cs model. This research regarded the academic committee as a team and analyzed the reasons for the low operating efficiency of the academic committee from the perspective of how the team improves the work performance and proposed solutions. The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors affecting the operational efficiency of the Academic Committee and to make suggestions from the perspective of the Secretariat. The fundamental purpose is to improve the efficiency of the Academic Committee. Therefore, Hawkins's 5Cs model is a suitable framework on which to build. The following conceptual framework presents the exploration ideas of this study. The main factors affecting the operation of the academic committee have been reflected in the diagram of figure 1.

Figure 1. Hawkins's 5Cs model

Members are the essential elements of academic committees. The selection of members is the first factor affecting the operation of academic committees. The committee members are the main body of academic governance implemented by the academic committee (Yu & Liu, 2023). Therefore, members' age, educational level, ability to express opinions independently, global vision and sense of discipline are all factors that affect the operational efficiency of academic committees.

The position, purpose, and goal of academic committees and the rights and obligations of academic committee members are the operational bases that need to be clarified. Only when the duties and powers are clearly defined can academic committee members determine the expected direction of efforts. A perfect, concrete, and feasible system guarantees the safeguarding of the academic autonomy of universities.

By jointly developing academic committees' statutes and rules of procedure, members agree on the working process and code of conduct of academic committees. And create a shared awareness that members are collectively responsible for the university's appointments and academic committees' objectives. When a member's interests conflict with the interests of academic committees, it shall be handled according to the consensus reached in advance.

Academic committees need to consider the needs and aspirations of stakeholders such as universities' administrations, faculties, students, and other academic organizations within universities to achieve a win-win situation for all parties. The relationship between academic committees and external academic organizations and the division of labor is unclear, resulting in the cross-duplication of organizational functions and separate administration or prevarication.

The members' academic level must continuously improve as universities' highest academic institution. At the same time, members should continue to learn how to play academic committees' responsibilities better. Whether academic committees have a platform and support for members' promotion should also be considered as a factor affecting the operation of academic committees.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Based on the existing problems of the Academic Committee, this study explores the deep-seated reasons and puts forward suggestions for optimizing the operation of the Academic Committee. This makes the study qualitative research. This study is a case study conducted around a particular university. Gerring (2006) pointed out that an in-depth study of a single case can be considered a case study. This study adopts the interview method to investigate the respondents from the purposive sampling. The interviews will be semi-structured. Respondents' views and expectations of the Academic Committee are presented through their positions.

THE UNIVERSITY CONTEXT

The study was conducted at a medical university in Shandong Province, China. The Academic Committee of the university has 27 members, including one chairman and two deputy chairmen. The Secretariat is located in the Development Planning Department. The Chief of the Development Planning Department serves as Secretary-General. The Deputy Directors of the Human Resources Department, the Office of Discipline Development, the Academic Affairs Department, and the Science and Technology Department serve as Deputy Secretaries-General. The university has fifteen faculties and five directly affiliated hospitals. The university has thirty-one majors covering five disciplines: medicine, management, science, engineering, and education.

RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The researcher used purposive sampling to select the subjects as research respondents. A total of ten employees from the university were chosen to participate in the study. Five of them are members of the Academic Committee. The other five are from the Department of Development Planning, the Human Resources Department, the Office of Discipline Development, the Academic Affairs Department, and the Science and Technology Department. The researchers interviewed them about the problems in the operation of the university's academic committee.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS PROCEDURES

The study employed a series of interviews as research instruments. The paper presents a case study based on in-depth interviews with ten staff. They are members of Academic Committees or employees of relevant functional departments. The interviews were semi-structured and qualitative, covering the operation of the Academic Committee. The interview questions for the participants were framed based on the conceptual framework and research questions. The interviews were conducted face-to-face, according to the respondents' preferred time. In the

interview, participants were first introduced to the purpose of the study to ensure that they fully understood the study. This study identified the members as M1, M2, M3, M4 and M5, while staff from functional departments are identified as S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5. By sorting out the interview copy, the problems and dilemmas faced in the operation of the Academic Committee reflected by the interviewees were classified. We got 17 questions by collating them, which the researchers divided into six aspects by theme.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION AND TRUSTWORTHINESS

Before participating in the study, the investigator personally contacted and confirmed that the participants agreed to participate in the interview. Before the interview, inform the participants about the topic of the interview. The research was carried out in China. Therefore, the interviews were conducted in Chinese. All participants were treated equally and fairly regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, or culture. Furthermore, make sure they do not feel uncomfortable in the study. To protect the privacy of the participants, no personal information was disclosed.

RESULTS

PROBLEMS IN THE OPERATION OF THE ACADEMIC COMMITTEE AND THE DEEP CAUSES

1. Unlike the duties specified in the Articles of Association, the Academic Committee focuses on fewer significant affairs, such as developing disciplines and training talent at the university level, and more on micro-office work.
2. For administrative departments, the Academic Committee exists just because individual workflows must be approved before proceeding. Alternatively, use the Academic Committee to avoid liability.

The analysis of the above issues indicates that although academic committees should decide academic affairs, administrative departments still dominate with their administrative power. The Academic Committee is only a tool attached to administrative power and rarely plays a substantive role. The supreme academic authority of the Academic Committee is not represented. Overall, the Academic Committee's position is unclear, and the academic power is weak.

We are sometimes reluctant to attend academic committee meetings because it is useless to attend, and the final decision maker is the university administration. In some cases, the proposal of the administration department is discussed and approved by the university leaders, and the next day, it is submitted to the Provincial Education Department. The proposal submitted to the Academic Committee for consideration is just "going through the process," and it is useless for us to disagree. (M2)

3. The proportion of members who hold or have held administrative positions is relatively high.
4. The overall age of the members is too high, and the age structure is unreasonable.
5. The distribution of academic disciplines to which members belong is seriously unbalanced.

6. As a medical university, the proportion of doctors in affiliated hospitals with strong practical abilities and high academic levels is small.

According to the charter of the Academic Committee of the case university, members should, in principle, be professors, and a certain number of young teachers are required. Although the committee's composition can meet the constitution's requirements, it also shows the deviation of age structure, academic structure and post background. Due to these deviations, there are some phenomena in the operation of the meeting organization and the expression of unfair opinions. These biases can be summarized as the unreasonable composition of the Committee.

Four are retired, and five more are retiring in the next two months. Now, the meeting cannot be organized if the remaining members have one person absent and the number of conferences does not meet the statutory requirements. (S1)

Some of the members are from the same faculty, and the dean of the faculty is on the Committee. Some members dare not express their views in front of the leaders. They disagree with the leaders in their hearts and do not say anything because of the leaders' faces. (M1)

7. The charter of the university Academic Committee was copied from the state document and was not revised according to the actual situation of the university.

8. The organization of the meeting is not standardized, and the meeting is often held on urgent notice.

9. Some topics do not fall within the responsibility of the Academic Committee and have to be met for discussion only because of administrative requirements.

The Ministry of Education promulgated the Regulations on Academic Committees of Institutions of Higher Education to standardize academic committees' basic system and principles. However, at the same time, it also reserves enough space for universities to formulate the academic committee charter based on the actual situation. Based on the above problems, the university failed to use "space" well. The lack of appropriate codes of conduct or the failure to implement institutional requirements led to confusion in the organization and operation of meetings. In the final analysis, the operation mechanism is not sound, and the management is not standardized.

There are so many meetings that the committee members are swamped. It feels like the Academic Committee is the only research institute in the university for all academic affairs. (M1)

10. When some professors participate in academic decision-making, they often appear to lack management knowledge and decision-making ability, or they only consider problems from their disciplinary background, and their decision-making vision is narrow.

11. Some professors even ask for workload when participating in the university's academic affairs.

12. Some members lack a sense of responsibility and are often absent.

All these reflect the imbalance of professors' research levels and the difference in members' ability to perform their duties. To realize professors' academic governance, professors must have the good academic ability. Professors should have the corresponding teaching and academic level, independent academic personality, cooperation and tolerance, and scientific management and decision-making ability.

We welcome the opinions of professors, but sometimes, some Committee members only put forward opinions from a personal perspective or on behalf of a faculty and do not perform their duties from the perspective of the university as a whole. Their opinions sometimes run counter to the interests of the university. (S5)

13. Some teachers and most students do not know about the Academic Committee.

14. The needs and aspirations of stakeholders, such as young teachers and students, are sometimes overlooked.

15. The Undergraduate Teaching Steering Committee and Academic Degree Evaluation Committee have certain administrative functions. Their Secretariats are set in the Academic Affairs Department and the Office of Discipline Development. Top-down administrative lines drive their operation, so there is no very close connection between them and the Academic Committee of the university

The relationship between the Academic Committee and external stakeholders such as faculty, students, administrative departments, and other academic organizations is poorly connected. This situation can lead to the Academic Committee ignoring the needs and desires of stakeholders, leading to bias in decision-making.

16. There are few members' training programs.

17. There is less support for members' personal development.

Regular review, consolidation, and improvement are essential if a team wants to progress. Group learning and individual learning should be carried out simultaneously and cooperate. Members are the cornerstone of academic committees. If we want to improve the performance ability of the academic committee, we need to indirectly improve the performance ability of the committee members. Training members to improve their academic level, responsibilities and deliberate ability is necessary. The Academic Committee lacks the means of reflection and improvement support.

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY

1. Clarify the position of the Academic Committee and institutionalize academic power.

It is clearly stated in the Charter of the Academic Committee that the Academic Committee is the highest academic institution of the university, and it is the institution that coordinates the decision-making, deliberation, evaluation, and consultation of academic affairs. The members of the Academic Committee participate in the revision of the Articles of Association and Rules of Procedure of the Academic Committee and jointly formulate the working process and code of conduct of the Academic Committee. According to the actual situation of the university, the specific responsibilities and authority in the construction of disciplines, teaching, scientific research, talents, and learning styles are detailed. The above operations clarify the position and duties of the Academic Committee, and the academic power is guaranteed in the system.

2. Improve the composition mechanism and decision-making mechanism of the Academic Committee.

The Academic Committee Secretariat shall comprehensively consider and adjust primary membership criteria based on age, academic level, adherence to regulations and principles, and concern for the university's development. According to the situation of the case university, increasing the proportion of doctors in affiliated hospitals is suggested. Moreover, amend the method for the election of members. To ensure the next election of members, members of the age structure are reasonable and have a sense of discipline and responsibility. The more feasible methods are as follows: first, limit the proportion of members of more prominent faculties in the total number of members. Safeguard the number of members of smaller faculties. Protect the interests of smaller faculties as far as possible. And promote fairness at the starting point. The second is to comprehensively consider various factors in the actual situation, such as faculties, disciplines and professional structures, and adopt the combination of old, middle-aged, and young people to increase the number of members. While considering the universality of the composition of representatives, it also pays attention to the rationality and scientific design of members. Third, real-name voting is adopted in decision-making methods. The Academic Committee is a responsibility and honor, and scholars will cherish this honor. The real-name voting system is conducive to clear commitment and reduces favor and favoritism votes.

3. Set up subdivisions. Not only improve work efficiency but also realize the decentralization of responsibilities.

Under the Academic Committee, to set up a series of special committees for subdivisions. The Academic Committee entrusts special committees to perform specific academic management and academic review affairs on behalf of the Academic Committee. This kind of decentralization of responsibilities avoids the practical problem that it is hard to convene plenary meetings due to the large number of members of the Academic Committee and improves work efficiency. At the same time, establish academic committees of faculties, expand democracy at the grass-roots level, and promote academic democracy from the bottom up. Academic committees of the faculties deliberate significant issues such as disciplines, teaching, scientific research, and talent teams of the faculty; listen to the report of the administrative head of the college and the head of the grass-roots academic organization on the annual work plan and the year-end work summary; and is responsible for the maintenance of the university's academic style and the construction of academic ethics.

4. Strengthen the connection of stakeholders and promote joint governance of the university.

Carry out top-level design and coordinate the relationship between the Academic Committee and existing academic organizations in the university. Considering the relationship between administrative power and academic power, the rational choice is that administrative power entrusts academic decision-making and the corresponding resource allocation power to academic power. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms can be introduced if necessary, such as setting up seats for the Academic Committee meetings and allowing students, faculty, and other stakeholders to sit in. To encourage the Academic Committee to contribute its specific knowledge and wisdom through relevant regulations and incentive mechanisms to complete the academic governance consistent with the university's goals and the interests of teachers and students. The aim is to encourage the university's growth by fostering an academic community. Strengthening engagement with stakeholders means taking on shared responsibility. The objective is to discover methods for constructing a superior university. Only an excellent and unified university can cultivate more and better talents, produce better scientific research, and serve the public better so that every citizen can benefit from it.

5. Increase the input of resources and guide the Academic Committee.

Provide funds, venues, services, and other support for the Academic Committee. Moreover, guide members to reflect and improve. At the same time, the academic committee should provide some support for members' personal development and academic improvement. Continuously guide members to strengthen the recognition of the purpose and objectives of the Academic Committee. Improve the academic governance level of members. Strengthen the cohesion and level of cooperation among members. Through reflection, improvement, and strengthening, members can be more explicit about the positioning and responsibilities of the Academic Committee to make more effective decisions on academic affairs. Then, the operational efficiency of the Academic Committee will be improved.

LIMITATION

One of the limitations of this study is the single research method and the participation of participants. Most participants were so busy at work that they could only spare a little time to cooperate with the study. Due to time constraints, some interviews were not in-depth. Second, the study interviewed only five commissioners and five employees from the administration and did not involve other stakeholders, such as teachers, students, and administrations, who do not serve as commissioners. Third, a survey of one university cannot summarize all the factors affecting the efficiency of academic committees' operation in other similar universities.

DISCUSSION

Through research, we find the problems in the operation of academic committees in local universities, classify them, and discuss their deep reasons. "Unreasonable composition of members" and "unbalanced ability of members to perform their duties" echoed the views of Yu and Liu (2023) and Li and Su (2020). There are cases where the academic governance process mentioned by Huang and Lin (2022) is too simple, and the needs and aspirations of students are ignored by Wei (2016). At the same time, it is also found that the charter of the academic committee copied the national document and did not adjust according to the actual situation of the university, so the practical applicability of the charter is low, resulting in poor operation. With the help of Hawkins' 5c model, we do find a lack of member training and support for individual member development. Based on the 5c model, members' personal development should be valued. We do not rule out other problems in the operation of the Academic Committee. In the next step, we plan to monitor whether there is any change in stakeholders' satisfaction with the Academic Committee before and after the implementation of the recommendations to improve the operation of the Academic Committee, to further identify feasible measures to improve the efficiency of the Academic Committee.

CONCLUSION

This study considers the Academic Committee as a team, analyses the factors that affect efficiency from the perspective of improving team performance, and analyses the deep-seated reasons for these problems. In addition, based on the perspective of the Secretariat of the Academic Committee, this study also puts forward some suggestions to improve the efficiency of the Academic Committee. The research shows that the Academic Committee needs to take different measures to improve and strengthen two dimensions: internal and external, task and process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank UNITAR International University for the support of the publication of this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Guo T. & Sun Q. (2020). The Organizational Structure of Academic Committee of Research-intensive Universities in China. *Higher Education Exploration*, (11), 19-24.
- Huang M., & Lin Q. (2022). On the Logic for Academic Governance in Higher Education Institutions. *Educational Research*, (08), 141-148.
- Gerring, J. (2006). *Case Study Research : Principles and Practices*. Cambridge University Press.
- Li C., Liu S. & Su Y. (2018). Governance Structure and Relations at Chinese Higher Education Institutions: A Survey of 75 Higher Education Institutions Affiliated with the Ministry of Education. *Journal of Dalian University of Technology (Social Sciences)*, (05), 105-111. doi: 10.19525/j.issn1008-407x.2018.05.014.
- Li F. & Su Y. (2020). A Governance Value-oriented Research on the Charter of Academic Committee: A Text Analysis of 22 Charters of the Academic Committee of "Double Tops" University. *Research in Educational Development*, (19), 33-41, doi: 10.14121/j.cnki.1008-3855.2020.19.010.
- Liao X. (2019). Public Reason and Practical Logic of University Academic Committee. *Fudan Education Forum*, 17(01),24-30. doi:10.13397/j.cnki.fef.2019.01.006
- Liu H. & Wang M. (2021). A Comparative Study on Internal Governance Structures of Chinese and American Public Universities—A Case Study of University of California and A University. *Journal of University of Shanghai for Science and Technology*, 43(04), 392-398. doi: 10.13256/j.cnki.jusst.sse.2021.04.015
- Peter H. (2011). *Leadership Team Coaching: Developing collective transformational leadership. (2nd edition)*. Kogan Page Limited.
- Tian F. (2022). Study on the Influencing Factors of the Function of Academic Committees in First-class University Colleges in China. *Modern Education Science*, (04), 24-31. doi: 10.13980/j.cnki.xdjyxx.2022.04.05
- Wang H. (2022). On the Five Basic Propositions Facing the High-quality Development of Higher Education. *The Scientific Exploration of Education*, 40(1), 4-12.
- Wang W., & Ruan L. (2022). Institutional Ideals and Practical Dilemmas for University Academic Committees to Participate in Governance. *Fudan Education Forum*, (03),35-43. doi:10.13397/j.cnki.fef.2022.03.002.
- Wang W., & Wang H. (2022). Academic Logic and Administrative Incentives: The Dualtrack Governance Mechanism of Chinese Universities. *University Education Science*, (02),28-36. 1672-0717(2022)02-0028-09
- Wei X. (2016). On the Operating Effectiveness of Academic Committee in Universities in Mainland China. *Research in Educational Development*, (19), 63-69, doi: 10.14121/j.cnki.1008-3855.2016.19.012.
- Yu L. & Liu Y. (2023). Diagnosis and Optimization of the Effectiveness of University Academic Governance System Construction: Focus on the Historical Revisions to the "Double First-

Class" Construction Universities' Academic Board Codes. *Fudan Education Forum*, 21(1), 28-43, doi: 10.3969/j.issn.1672-0059.2023.01.005

Yu N. (2020). Exploration and reflection on the construction of academic committees in universities. *University Education*. (04), 186-188

Zhang D., Wang Q. & Cai S. (2020). Why Academic Committees are Marginalized in the Internal Governance of Colleges and Universities: A Case Study of University A. *Jiangsu Higher Education*, (10), 29-36, doi: 10.13236/j.cnki.jshe.2020.10.005

Zhang H. & Yue M. (2019). President and Academic Committee: Enlightenment of Universities' Diversified Governance Practice. *Modern Education Science*, (11), 44-52, doi: 10.13980/j.cnki.xdjykyx.2019.11.008